

A Comparative Study of Job Satisfaction between Primary and Secondary Female School Teachers of Ranchi Town

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Abstract:-

➤ Aim-

The purpose of the present study is to job satisfaction among primary and secondary female school teachers of Ranchi.

➤ Method-

Samples were selected by stratified random sampling method. For that 80 teachers were selected randomly from different schools of Ranchi. The job satisfaction scale developed by Dixit (1993) and a personal data questionnaire were used for data collection. Data were treated by Percentage, Mean, SD, and Anova.

➤ Result-

The average degree of job satisfaction was observed in 32% of the teachers in the whole sample group. When compared to primary school teachers, secondary school teachers, had a higher percentage of job satisfaction (32%). Type of school had an F value of 0.95, which was statistically not significant, and salary had an F value of 4.53 which was statistically significant at the 0.01 level. The interactional effect of the type of school and salary had an F value of 6.83, which was statistically significant.

➤ Conclusion-

Job satisfaction was found to varying degrees across the entire group. The type of school and salary interactions on job satisfaction was statistically significant. The type of school and salary have a big influence on job satisfaction.

Keywords:- Job Satisfaction, Type of School, and Salary.

I. INTRODUCTION

The degree of job satisfaction a worker experiences may be indicative of how they see their work. It is not the same as motivation; rather, it deals with a person's mindset and psychological state with regard to a given task. For example, it might be connected to a sense of self-worth and therefore affected or motivated by factors like pay, supervisory style, and age. If a person's psychological or physical requirements are not being addressed by their current job, job satisfaction may be low.

Job satisfaction levels can vary. Usually, it is based on the employee's viewpoint. An individual's good attitude towards their employment is referred to as job satisfaction. Any form of labour necessitates a specific mental state from the worker. One person may feel content with their work, while another person may experience discontent with the same company, depending on how they approach their work.

The future of India will be decided by the calibre of its educational system, which in turn will be determined by how knowledgeable and well-prepared the teachers are. The continuously changing educational environment calls for teachers who are highly effective and goal-oriented. Education's goal is to assist students in internalising knowledge, abilities, and attitudes so they are equipped to take on the responsibilities of promoting society's ideals and achieving social objectives. Dissemination of knowledge is no longer the only goal of education.

Education is the process of developing a person's potential and the intrinsic abilities and interests of a population. In other words, education not only brings out a child's intrinsic potential but also meets society expectations by raising population productivity, which in turn raises the standard of life (Jalaja C, 2007). The education system should be centered on the all-around development of human personality from the early school years in order to accomplish this. School teachers are the primary players to carry out these goals.

Understanding the situation of the educational system as a whole and its capacity to carry out its duty of creating future citizens who are aware and educated in keeping with the national vision, one of whose pillars reads: A prosperous, productive, and innovative, is crucial. Due to the numerous changes that have taken place in the national and international educational systems, it is important to understand how these changes have affected those in charge of running secondary schools.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Nagar (2012) researched "Organisational commitment and job satisfaction among teachers during times of Burnout for developing and testing a model for Burnout and its effect on job satisfaction on organizational commitment." According to research, female teachers had higher mean

scores for organizational commitment and job satisfaction than male instructors.

Mehta (2012) To determine whether the perception of job happiness among teachers was influenced by the kind of organization (private vs. govt.) and the gender (male vs. female), research on job satisfaction among teachers was conducted. T-tests and descriptive analysis were used to compare how men and women perceived their job satisfaction. The findings indicated that there would be a big disparity between instructors at public and private schools in terms of job satisfaction.

Kumar & Bhatia (2011) To compare the job satisfaction among Physical Education teachers and their attitude towards teaching, it was noted that the level of job satisfaction and the attitude of the teachers towards teaching is least affected by gender, marital status, the minimum qualification, and the income group.

Akhtar and Naqvi (2010) did a comparison of the job satisfaction of instructors at public and private schools. It was hypothesized that instructors employed by public and private schools experienced similar levels of job satisfaction. The job satisfaction of teachers in public and private schools did not differ significantly, according to the data analysis performed using the t-test and ANOVA.

➤ *Objectives*

The following objectives were prepared for the present study:

- To assess the level of job satisfaction among primary and secondary female school teachers of Ranchi.
- To find out the impact of the type of school (government and private) and amount of salary (high and low) on the level of satisfaction among primary and secondary female school teachers.

➤ *Hypotheses*

The following hypotheses were prepared for verification:

- The level of job satisfaction will vary in primary and secondary female school teachers of Ranchi.
- There will be a significant impact of the type of school and the amount of salary on the level of job satisfaction among primary and secondary female school teachers.

➤ *Sample Design*

The present study has been conducted on eighty school teachers equally divided into two groups of type of school (government and private), and two groups of the amount of salary (high and low). Thus, samples have been formed 2x2= 4 strata. From each stratum, 20 students have been selected making a total of 80 students.

Table 1 Sample Design

Salary	Type of school		Total
	Government School	Private school	
High (35000&above)	20	20	40
Low (25000&below)	20	20	40
Total	40	40	80

➤ *Tools*

The following tools have been used in the present study:-

- *Personal Data Questionnaire (PDQ).*
- *Job Satisfaction Scale*

• *Personal Data Questionnaire (PDQ).*

A personal data questionnaire or PDQ is a list of questions to get information about a subject. This questionnaire was prepared by the researcher to collect data concerning the characteristics of the subjects such as name, age, gender, religion education residence, etc.

• *Job Satisfaction Scale.*

The job satisfaction scale developed by Dixit (1993) was used to measure the job satisfaction of teachers. It is a Likert-type five-point scale having 58 items. The reliability of this scale is .85 by the split-half method and the .75 test re-test method.

➤ *Instruction for Administration.*

- It is a self-administered scale and can be used for groups of any reasonable size. It may also be used individually.
- There is no time limit ordinarily an individual task. One hour to complete the scale.

• *Scoring.*

Scoring is on a five-point scale from one to five. For the response of “strongly agree” the score is 1 and for “disagree” it is 2, for “undecided” 3 marks are allotted for “agree” scoring is 4, and for “strongly disagree” it is 5.

➤ *Procedure:-*

As previously indicated, various schools from Ranchi were chosen at random for the study's samples. Twenty instances were chosen for each of the four sub-groups and a personal data questionnaire was used to collect information on factors including instructor type, income, and other factors. The investigator gave the subjects a test to gauge their level of job satisfaction. The subjects are given the appropriate amount of time between the administration of two tests.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) can be used to analyse the data. The hypothesis, which can be evaluated with the aid of the respondents' response sheets on the suicidal ideation scale, was scored and statistically analysed using percentage, mean, SD, and ANOVAs. The SPSS results are listed in Table.

➤ *Level of Job Satisfaction Among Primary and Secondary Female School Teachers of Ranchi.*

Number and percentage of job satisfaction level of primary and secondary female school teachers of Ranchi are presented in table 1 and figure 2.

Table 2 Level of Job Satisfaction Among Primary and Secondary Female School Teachers of Ranchi

Sample groups	Very low	Low	Average	Good	Highest
Primary teachers (40)	22.5%	30%	32.5%	15%	0%
Secondary teachers(40)	17.5%	22.5%	27.5%	32.5%	0%

Fig 1 Level of Job Satisfaction Among Primary and Secondary Female School Teachers

➤ *Impact of Type of School and Amount of Salary on Job Satisfaction Among Primary and Secondary Female School Teachers of Ranchi.*

Finding the main interaction effect of school type and wage amount on job satisfaction among primary and secondary female school teachers in Ranchi was one of the key goals of the most recent research. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results were computed and shown in table 2

Table 3 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Showing the Impact of Type of School and Amount of Salary on Job Satisfaction Among Primary and Secondary Female School Teachers of Ranchi

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	F ratio	P
Main Effects					
A. Type of School	185.01	1	185.01	0.95	NS
B. Amount of Salary	876.10	1	876.10	4.53*	0.01
2 way interaction AXB	1318.50	1	1318.50	6.83**	0.01
Within treatment	14678.50	76	193.14		

**Significant at 0.01

NS:-Not Significant

* Significant at 0.05

Looking at the above table demonstrates how important an impact money has on job satisfaction. At 0.01 levels, the obtained F value of 4.53 was statistically significant. As a result, the compensation received had a distinct impact on job satisfaction. However, research found that the type of school had little bearing on job satisfaction.

Statistics showed that the F value of 0.95 was not significant. Therefore, the supposition that "there will be a significant effect of type of school on job satisfaction among primary and secondary female school teachers of Ranchi" Was rejected. The interactional effect of amount of salary and type of school were found significant at 0.01 levels.

Table 4 Mean Scores of High and Low Salaried on Job Satisfaction

Group	N	Mean	SD	Mean difference	df	t Value	P
High salaried	40	131.98	19.73	12.27	78	2.01	P<0.05
Low salaried	40	144.25	21.62				

Figure 2 Mean score of High and Low salaried on Job Satisfaction

As shown in Table 2, the mean score for those with high salaries was 131.98, while that for those with low salaries was 144.25. The difference in mean scores between female school instructors earning high salaries and those earning low salaries was 12.27. This demonstrates that female school teachers who earned higher salaries had higher levels of job satisfaction than those who earned lower salaries. Female school instructors who earned high salaries and low salaries had SDs of 19.73 and 21.62, respectively. At 0.05 levels, the obtained t-ratio of 2.01 was significant. In light of this, the following hypothesis has been made: "There will be a significant impact of salary amount on job satisfaction among primary and secondary female school teachers of Ranchi." was approved.

IV. CONCLUSION

The following hypothesis was given as a result: "There would be significant main and interaction influence of type of school and salary on job satisfaction of female teachers of Ranchi." is acceptable from the standpoint of the type of school. As a result, it was determined that teachers in elementary and secondary schools experienced diverse levels of job satisfaction, and this was recognised in the context of pay. As a consequence, it was determined that teachers earning high salaries and low salaries both experienced equal levels of job satisfaction, and the hypothesis regarding the connection between the kind of school and salary was approved. According to the F-ratio, there are considerable differences in job satisfaction levels. As a consequence, it was discovered that instructors earning

high salaries and low salaries both experienced equal levels of job satisfaction, supporting the theory regarding the type of school and wage.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Bishay, A. (1996). Teacher motivation and job satisfaction: a study employing the experience sampling method. *Journal of Undergraduate Sciences*, 3, 147-154.
- [2]. Bolin, F. (2007). A study of teacher job satisfaction and factors that influence it. *Chinese educational Society*, 40(5):47-64.
- [3]. Cetin, Munevver Olcum. (2006). The Relationship Between Job Satisfaction, Occupational and Organizational Commitment of Academics. *Journal of American Academy of Business, Cambridge*, 8(1), pp 78-88 and pp. 11.
- [4]. Crossman, A. and Harris, P. (2006). Job satisfaction of secondary school teachers. *Educational Management and Leadership*, Vol. 34 No. 1, 29-46.
- [5]. Davidson, E. (2007). The Pivotal Role of Teacher Motivation in Tanzania. *The Educational Forum*, 157-166.
- [6]. Hulin, C.L., and Smith, P.C. (1964). Sex difference in job satisfaction. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 48:88-92.
- [7]. Jaiyeoba, AO. & Jibril, A. (2008). A study of job satisfaction of secondary school administrators in Kano state, Nigeria. *An International Multi-Disciplinary Journal*, 2(2): 94-107.

- [8]. Jabnoun, Naceur, Chan Yen Fook (2001). Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers in Selangor, Malaysia. *International Journal of Commerce and Management*, 11(3/4), pp 72 and pp 19.
- [9]. Koustelios, A.D. (2001). Personal Characteristics and Job Satisfaction of Greek Teachers. *The International Journal of Educational Management*, 15, No. 7, 354-538.
- [10]. Kumari, S., & Jafri, S. (2011). „Level of Organizational Commitment of Male and Female Teachers of Secondary Schools“. *Journal of Community Guidance & Research*
- [11]. Lukuyani, M. (2002). “A study of the Factors Contributing to Job-Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction among Secondary School teachers in Turkana District”, Unpublished PhD Thesis, Nairobi.
- [12]. Mehta, D. S. (2012). Job Satisfaction among Teachers“. *International Journal of Research in Commerce IT & Management*, 2(4), 77-83.
- [13]. Mehta, D. S. (2011). Teachers and their attitude towards teaching“. *Journal of research in Business Management*, 2(9), 32-43.
- [14]. Nagar, k. (2012, April). Organizational commitment and job satisfaction among teachers during times of Burnout“. *Vikalpa*, 37.2, 43-60
- [15]. Rasku , A., & Kinnunen, U. (2003). Job Conditions and Wellness among Finnish Upper Secondary School Teachers. *Psychology and Health*, 18 No. 4, 441-456.
- [16]. Tasnim, S. (2006). Job Satisfaction among Female Teachers: A Study on primary schools in Bangladesh. *Bergen: University of Bergen* (Unpublished Thesis).
- [17]. Yezzi, J.A. and Lester, D. (2000). Job Satisfaction in Teachers. *Psychological Reports*, 87(3), pp. 776.